

Cornered Magic Squares of Order 6

Whole the work can be accessed at the link

<https://numbers-magic.com/?p=8923>.

Inder J. Taneja¹

Abstract

*This work brings for the first time in the history of magic squares a new kind of magic square of order 6. It is called cornered magic square of order 6. It contains at the corner a pandiagonal magic square of order 4. Before to this the author [34] also introduced a new kind of magic square of order 6 based on magic rectangle of order 4×6 . Using **pandiagonal** magic square of order 4, we have written four different kinds of cornered magic squares of order 6. Based on these four cornered magic squares of order 6, we have written some examples of magic squares of orders 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16.*

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1	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA	111				
17	22	11	24	29	8	111
12	23	18	21	27	10	111
26	13	20	15	35	2	111
19	16	25	14	9	28	111
4	3	36	30	6	32	111
33	34	1	7	5	31	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

2	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA	111				
29	8	17	22	11	24	111
35	2	12	23	18	21	111
27	10	26	13	20	15	111
9	28	19	16	25	14	111
6	32	30	36	4	3	111
5	31	7	1	33	34	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

3	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA	111				
6	32	30	36	3	4	111
5	31	7	1	34	33	111
9	28	17	22	11	24	111
35	2	12	23	18	21	111
27	10	26	13	20	15	111
29	8	19	16	25	14	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

4	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA	111				
3	4	36	30	6	32	111
34	33	1	7	5	31	111
17	22	11	24	9	28	111
12	23	18	21	27	10	111
26	13	20	15	35	2	111
19	16	25	14	29	8	111
111	111	111	111	111	111	111

Based on these four magic squares we shall write some magic squares of orders 8, 10, 12, 14 and 16. These given in following sections.

2 Magic Squares of Order 8

Below are four magic square of order 8 formed by cornered magic squares of order 6

1	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA	260						
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260
5	31	36	25	38	43	22	60	260
6	26	37	32	35	41	24	59	260
11	40	27	34	29	49	16	54	260
61	33	30	39	28	23	42	4	260
56	18	17	50	44	20	46	9	260
55	47	48	15	21	19	45	10	260
58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

2	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA	260						
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260
5	43	22	31	36	25	38	60	260
6	49	16	26	37	32	35	59	260
11	41	24	40	27	34	29	54	260
61	23	42	33	30	39	28	4	260
56	20	46	44	50	18	17	9	260
55	19	45	21	15	47	48	10	260
58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

3	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA							260
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260
5	20	46	44	50	17	18	60	260
6	19	45	21	15	48	47	59	260
11	23	42	31	36	25	38	54	260
61	49	16	26	37	32	35	4	260
56	41	24	40	27	34	29	9	260
55	43	22	33	30	39	28	10	260
58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

4	Inder J. Taneja @IJTANEJA							260
8	2	62	64	51	13	53	7	260
5	17	18	50	44	20	46	60	260
6	48	47	15	21	19	45	59	260
11	31	36	25	38	23	42	54	260
61	26	37	32	35	41	24	4	260
56	40	27	34	29	49	16	9	260
55	33	30	39	28	43	22	10	260
58	63	3	1	14	52	12	57	260
260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260	260

3 Magic Squares of Order 10

Below are eight magic square of order 10 formed by cornered magic squares of order 6

1	https://numbers-magic.com/							@IJTANEJA		505
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505
25	76	49	54	43	56	61	40	91	10	505
75	26	44	55	50	53	59	42	89	12	505
27	74	58	45	52	47	67	34	88	13	505
73	28	51	48	57	46	41	60	14	87	505
72	29	36	35	68	62	38	64	86	15	505
70	31	65	66	33	39	37	63	16	85	505
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

2	https://numbers-magic.com/							@IJTANEJA		505
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505
25	76	61	40	49	54	43	56	91	10	505
75	26	67	34	44	55	50	53	89	12	505
27	74	59	42	58	45	52	47	88	13	505
73	28	41	60	51	48	57	46	14	87	505
72	29	38	64	62	68	36	35	86	15	505
70	31	37	63	39	33	65	66	16	85	505
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

3	https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA										505
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505	
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505	
25	76	38	64	62	68	35	36	91	10	505	
75	26	37	63	39	33	66	65	89	12	505	
27	74	41	60	49	54	43	56	88	13	505	
73	28	67	34	44	55	50	53	14	87	505	
72	29	59	42	58	45	52	47	86	15	505	
70	31	61	40	51	48	57	46	16	85	505	
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505	
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

4	https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA										505
3	1	99	97	96	6	94	8	9	92	505	
98	100	2	4	5	95	7	93	11	90	505	
25	76	35	36	68	62	38	64	91	10	505	
75	26	66	65	33	39	37	63	89	12	505	
27	74	49	54	43	56	41	60	88	13	505	
73	28	44	55	50	53	59	42	14	87	505	
72	29	58	45	52	47	67	34	86	15	505	
70	31	51	48	57	46	61	40	16	85	505	
32	69	17	83	19	81	24	22	78	80	505	
30	71	84	18	82	20	77	79	23	21	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

5	https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA										505
49	54	43	56	61	40	27	78	21	76	505	
44	55	50	53	59	42	75	71	30	26	505	
58	45	52	47	67	34	24	32	69	77	505	
51	48	57	46	41	60	73	29	72	28	505	
36	35	68	62	38	64	79	70	31	22	505	
65	66	33	39	37	63	25	23	80	74	505	
86	14	89	16	10	88	7	96	1	98	505	
11	20	83	17	82	90	2	97	8	95	505	
92	81	18	84	19	9	100	3	94	5	505	
13	87	12	85	91	15	93	6	99	4	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

6	https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA										505
7	96	1	98	15	87	85	91	12	13	505	
2	97	8	95	90	17	82	20	83	11	505	
100	3	94	5	9	84	19	81	18	92	505	
93	6	99	4	88	14	16	10	89	86	505	
74	23	80	25	38	64	62	68	35	36	505	
26	70	31	75	37	63	39	33	66	65	505	
28	29	72	73	41	60	49	54	43	56	505	
77	71	30	24	67	34	44	55	50	53	505	
22	32	69	79	59	42	58	45	52	47	505	
76	78	21	27	61	40	51	48	57	46	505	
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	

7	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	505	8	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	505														
38	64	62	68	35	36	76	78	21	27	505	96	10	6	89	8	97	98	2	92	7	505
37	63	39	33	66	65	26	70	31	75	505	1	13	20	16	87	83	17	82	86	100	505
41	60	49	54	43	56	28	29	72	73	505	11	88	81	85	14	18	84	19	15	90	505
67	34	44	55	50	53	22	32	69	79	505	94	91	95	12	93	4	3	99	9	5	505
59	42	58	45	52	47	77	71	30	24	505	76	78	21	27	49	54	43	56	61	40	505
61	40	51	48	57	46	74	23	80	25	505	26	71	30	75	44	55	50	53	59	42	505
94	12	95	91	93	4	99	3	9	5	505	22	29	72	79	58	45	52	47	67	34	505
1	13	17	16	86	20	83	82	87	100	505	28	32	69	73	51	48	57	46	41	60	505
11	88	84	85	15	81	18	19	14	90	505	77	70	31	24	36	35	68	62	38	64	505
96	89	6	10	8	97	2	98	92	7	505	74	23	80	25	65	66	33	39	37	63	505
505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505	505

4 Magic Squares of Order 12

Below are fourteen magic square of order 12 formed by cornered magic squares of order 6

1	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	870	2	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	870																
4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135	870	4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135	870
141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10	870	141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10	870
37	108	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	13	132	870	37	108	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	13	132	870
107	38	45	71	76	65	78	83	62	100	131	14	870	107	38	45	83	62	71	76	65	78	100	131	14	870
106	39	46	66	77	72	75	81	64	99	130	15	870	106	39	46	89	56	66	77	72	75	99	130	15	870
40	105	51	80	67	74	69	89	56	94	16	129	870	40	105	51	81	64	80	67	74	69	94	16	129	870
33	112	101	73	70	79	68	63	82	44	17	128	870	33	112	101	63	82	73	70	79	68	44	17	128	870
111	34	96	58	57	90	84	60	86	49	127	18	870	111	34	96	60	86	84	90	58	57	49	127	18	870
110	35	95	87	88	55	61	59	85	50	126	19	870	110	35	95	59	85	61	55	87	88	50	126	19	870
36	109	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	20	125	870	36	109	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	20	125	870
115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24	870	115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24	870
30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121	870	30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

3	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA														870
4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135				870
141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10				870
37	108	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	13	132				870
107	38	45	60	86	84	90	57	58	100	131	14				870
106	39	46	59	85	61	55	88	87	99	130	15				870
40	105	51	63	82	71	76	65	78	94	16	129				870
33	112	101	89	56	66	77	72	75	44	17	128				870
111	34	96	81	64	80	67	74	69	49	127	18				870
110	35	95	83	62	73	70	79	68	50	126	19				870
36	109	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	20	125				870
115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24				870
30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121				870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

4	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA														870
4	1	143	142	5	139	138	8	9	12	134	135				870
141	144	2	3	140	6	7	137	136	133	11	10				870
37	108	48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	13	132				870
107	38	45	57	58	90	84	60	86	100	131	14				870
106	39	46	88	87	55	61	59	85	99	130	15				870
40	105	51	71	76	65	78	63	82	94	16	129				870
33	112	101	66	77	72	75	81	64	44	17	128				870
111	34	96	80	67	74	69	89	56	49	127	18				870
110	35	95	73	70	79	68	83	62	50	126	19				870
36	109	98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	20	125				870
115	114	32	29	25	119	118	28	122	123	21	24				870
30	31	113	116	120	26	27	117	23	22	124	121				870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

5	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA														870
9	12	132	11	141	130	101	44	53	94	47	96				870
140	119	27	21	123	5	107	38	48	95	54	93				870
14	125	31	114	20	131	99	46	98	49	92	51				870
143	19	36	109	126	2	45	100	91	52	97	50				870
138	122	110	35	23	7	42	104	102	108	40	39				870
1	128	113	32	17	144	41	103	43	37	105	106				870
3	24	33	112	121	142	60	86	84	90	57	58				870
6	120	111	34	25	139	59	85	61	55	88	87				870
135	18	30	115	127	10	63	82	71	76	65	78				870
137	28	116	29	117	8	89	56	66	77	72	75				870
129	22	118	124	26	16	81	64	80	67	74	69				870
15	133	13	134	4	136	83	62	73	70	79	68				870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

6	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA														870
9	12	132	11	141	130	39	40	108	102	42	104				870
140	119	27	21	123	5	106	105	37	43	41	103				870
14	125	31	114	20	131	53	94	47	96	45	100				870
143	19	36	109	126	2	48	95	54	93	99	46				870
138	122	110	35	23	7	98	49	92	51	107	38				870
1	128	113	32	17	144	91	52	97	50	101	44				870
3	24	33	112	121	142	71	76	65	78	83	62				870
6	120	111	34	25	139	66	77	72	75	81	64				870
135	18	30	115	127	10	80	67	74	69	89	56				870
137	28	116	29	117	8	73	70	79	68	63	82				870
129	22	118	124	26	16	58	57	90	84	60	86				870
15	133	13	134	4	136	87	88	55	61	59	85				870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

7	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											870
9	12	132	11	141	130	101	44	53	94	47	96	870
140	119	27	21	123	5	107	38	48	95	54	93	870
14	125	31	114	20	131	99	46	98	49	92	51	870
143	19	36	109	126	2	45	100	91	52	97	50	870
138	122	110	35	23	7	42	104	102	108	40	39	870
1	128	113	32	17	144	41	103	43	37	105	106	870
3	24	33	112	121	142	78	71	76	70	68	72	870
6	120	111	34	25	139	61	85	59	87	88	55	870
135	18	30	115	127	10	83	81	63	66	80	62	870
137	28	116	29	117	8	56	64	82	79	65	89	870
129	22	118	124	26	16	90	60	86	58	57	84	870
15	133	13	134	4	136	67	74	69	75	77	73	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

8	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											870
9	12	132	11	141	130	39	40	108	102	42	104	870
140	119	27	21	123	5	106	105	37	43	41	103	870
14	125	31	114	20	131	53	94	47	96	45	100	870
143	19	36	109	126	2	48	95	54	93	99	46	870
138	122	110	35	23	7	98	49	92	51	107	38	870
1	128	113	32	17	144	91	52	97	50	101	44	870
3	24	33	112	121	142	78	71	76	70	68	72	870
6	120	111	34	25	139	61	85	59	87	88	55	870
135	18	30	115	127	10	83	81	63	66	80	62	870
137	28	116	29	117	8	56	64	82	79	65	89	870
129	22	118	124	26	16	90	60	86	58	57	84	870
15	133	13	134	4	136	67	74	69	75	77	73	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

9	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											870
31	115	28	113	119	29	101	44	53	94	47	96	870
118	110	36	111	33	27	107	38	48	95	54	93	870
25	35	109	34	112	120	99	46	98	49	92	51	870
116	30	117	32	26	114	45	100	91	52	97	50	870
12	138	5	134	9	137	42	104	102	108	40	39	870
1	128	130	13	19	144	41	103	43	37	105	106	870
2	18	123	22	127	143	60	86	84	90	57	58	870
139	129	122	23	16	6	59	85	61	55	88	87	870
141	20	24	121	125	4	63	82	71	76	65	78	870
142	14	21	124	131	3	89	56	66	77	72	75	870
135	126	15	132	17	10	81	64	80	67	74	69	870
8	7	140	11	136	133	83	62	73	70	79	68	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

10	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											870
31	115	28	113	119	29	39	40	108	102	42	104	870
118	110	36	111	33	27	106	105	37	43	41	103	870
25	35	109	34	112	120	53	94	47	96	45	100	870
116	30	117	32	26	114	48	95	54	93	99	46	870
12	138	5	134	9	137	98	49	92	51	107	38	870
1	128	130	13	19	144	91	52	97	50	101	44	870
2	18	123	22	127	143	71	76	65	78	83	62	870
139	129	122	23	16	6	66	77	72	75	81	64	870
141	20	24	121	125	4	80	67	74	69	89	56	870
142	14	21	124	131	3	73	70	79	68	63	82	870
135	126	15	132	17	10	58	57	90	84	60	86	870
8	7	140	11	136	133	87	88	55	61	59	85	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

11	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	870								
31	115	28	113	119	29	101	44	53	94	47	96	870
118	110	36	111	33	27	107	38	48	95	54	93	870
25	35	109	34	112	120	99	46	98	49	92	51	870
116	30	117	32	26	114	45	100	91	52	97	50	870
12	138	5	134	9	137	42	104	102	108	40	39	870
1	128	130	13	19	144	41	103	43	37	105	106	870
2	18	123	22	127	143	78	71	76	70	68	72	870
139	129	122	23	16	6	61	85	59	87	88	55	870
141	20	24	121	125	4	83	81	63	66	80	62	870
142	14	21	124	131	3	56	64	82	79	65	89	870
135	126	15	132	17	10	90	60	86	58	57	84	870
8	7	140	11	136	133	67	74	69	75	77	73	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

12	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	870								
31	115	28	113	119	29	39	40	108	102	42	104	870
118	110	36	111	33	27	106	105	37	43	41	103	870
25	35	109	34	112	120	53	94	47	96	45	100	870
116	30	117	32	26	114	48	95	54	93	99	46	870
12	138	5	134	9	137	98	49	92	51	107	38	870
1	128	130	13	19	144	91	52	97	50	101	44	870
2	18	123	22	127	143	78	71	76	70	68	72	870
139	129	122	23	16	6	61	85	59	87	88	55	870
141	20	24	121	125	4	83	81	63	66	80	62	870
142	14	21	124	131	3	56	64	82	79	65	89	870
135	126	15	132	17	10	90	60	86	58	57	84	870
8	7	140	11	136	133	67	74	69	75	77	73	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

13	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	870								
48	42	102	104	91	53	93	47	27	30	119	114	870
45	60	86	84	90	57	58	100	120	35	110	25	870
46	59	85	61	55	88	87	99	28	112	33	117	870
51	63	82	71	76	65	78	94	113	109	36	32	870
95	89	56	66	77	72	75	50	116	34	111	29	870
96	81	64	80	67	74	69	49	31	115	26	118	870
101	83	62	73	70	79	68	44	19	127	14	130	870
98	103	43	41	54	92	52	97	132	23	122	13	870
7	144	137	4	140	3	37	108	16	22	123	129	870
139	133	11	136	10	6	107	38	125	124	21	20	870
2	12	134	9	135	143	106	39	128	121	24	17	870
142	1	8	141	5	138	40	105	15	18	131	126	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

14	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	@IJTANEJA	870								
48	42	102	104	53	91	93	47	115	32	29	114	870
45	71	76	65	78	83	62	100	30	113	116	31	870
46	66	77	72	75	81	64	99	3	6	143	138	870
101	80	67	74	69	89	56	44	137	136	9	8	870
51	73	70	79	68	63	82	94	4	133	12	141	870
96	58	57	90	84	60	86	49	144	11	134	1	870
95	87	88	55	61	59	85	50	140	10	135	5	870
98	103	43	41	92	54	52	97	7	139	2	142	870
16	129	23	121	20	124	128	19	39	108	33	110	870
130	15	18	27	117	120	26	127	34	109	40	107	870
131	14	123	118	28	25	119	22	112	35	106	37	870
13	132	126	24	125	21	17	122	105	38	111	36	870
870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870	870

5 Magic Squares of Order 14

Below are few examples of magic square of order 14 formed by cornered magic squares of order 6

1	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											1379	
1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
39	158	73	124	97	102	91	104	109	88	139	58	180	17	1379
157	40	123	74	92	103	98	101	107	90	137	60	179	18	1379
156	41	75	122	106	93	100	95	115	82	136	61	19	178	1379
155	42	121	76	99	96	105	94	89	108	62	135	20	177	1379
43	154	120	77	84	83	116	110	86	112	134	63	21	176	1379
44	153	118	79	113	114	81	87	85	111	64	133	175	22	1379
45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

2	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											1379	
1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
39	158	73	124	109	88	97	102	91	104	139	58	180	17	1379
157	40	123	74	115	82	92	103	98	101	137	60	179	18	1379
156	41	75	122	107	90	106	93	100	95	136	61	19	178	1379
155	42	121	76	89	108	99	96	105	94	62	135	20	177	1379
43	154	120	77	86	112	110	116	84	83	134	63	21	176	1379
44	153	118	79	85	111	87	81	113	114	64	133	175	22	1379
45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

3	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											1379		
	1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
	196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
	37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
	159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
	39	158	73	124	86	112	110	116	83	84	139	58	180	17	1379
	157	40	123	74	85	111	87	81	114	113	137	60	179	18	1379
	156	41	75	122	89	108	97	102	91	104	136	61	19	178	1379
	155	42	121	76	115	82	92	103	98	101	62	135	20	177	1379
	43	154	120	77	107	90	106	93	100	95	134	63	21	176	1379
	44	153	118	79	109	88	99	96	105	94	64	133	175	22	1379
	45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
	47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
	151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
	149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	

4	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA											1379		
	1	3	195	193	192	191	7	8	9	187	11	185	13	184	1379
	196	194	2	4	5	6	190	189	188	10	186	12	15	182	1379
	37	160	51	49	147	145	144	54	142	56	57	140	183	14	1379
	159	38	146	148	50	52	53	143	55	141	59	138	181	16	1379
	39	158	73	124	83	84	116	110	86	112	139	58	180	17	1379
	157	40	123	74	114	113	81	87	85	111	137	60	179	18	1379
	156	41	75	122	97	102	91	104	89	108	136	61	19	178	1379
	155	42	121	76	92	103	98	101	107	90	62	135	20	177	1379
	43	154	120	77	106	93	100	95	115	82	134	63	21	176	1379
	44	153	118	79	99	96	105	94	109	88	64	133	175	22	1379
	45	152	80	117	65	131	67	129	72	70	126	128	23	174	1379
	47	150	78	119	132	66	130	68	125	127	71	69	173	24	1379
	151	46	25	171	27	169	168	167	31	32	33	35	163	161	1379
	149	48	172	26	170	28	29	30	166	165	164	162	34	36	1379
1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	

20	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA												1379	
	74	68	128	130	117	79	119	73	12	190	5	186	9	189	1379
	71	86	112	110	116	83	84	126	193	180	182	13	19	4	1379
	72	85	111	87	81	114	113	125	2	18	21	176	179	195	1379
	77	89	108	97	102	91	104	120	191	181	24	173	16	6	1379
	127	115	82	92	103	98	101	70	1	14	175	22	183	196	1379
	122	107	90	106	93	100	95	75	187	20	174	23	177	10	1379
	121	109	88	99	96	105	94	76	194	178	15	184	17	3	1379
	124	129	69	67	80	118	78	123	8	7	192	11	188	185	1379
	36	169	26	167	25	170	163	32	65	134	59	136	141	56	1379
	166	156	42	157	44	38	154	31	60	135	66	133	139	58	1379
	29	158	48	45	151	150	39	168	138	61	132	63	147	50	1379
	162	37	149	152	46	47	160	35	131	64	137	62	57	140	1379
	33	43	155	40	153	159	41	164	52	51	148	142	54	144	1379
	165	28	171	30	172	27	34	161	145	146	49	55	53	143	1379
	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

23	mgc	Inder J. Taneja https://numbers-magic.com/ @IJTANEJA												1379	
	97	102	91	104	109	88	124	126	69	75	162	29	39	164	1379
	92	103	98	101	107	90	74	80	117	123	40	151	46	157	1379
	106	93	100	95	115	82	76	77	120	121	167	154	43	30	1379
	99	96	105	94	89	108	125	119	78	72	31	44	153	166	1379
	84	83	116	110	86	112	70	118	79	127	161	48	149	36	1379
	113	114	81	87	85	111	122	71	128	73	32	41	156	165	1379
	136	62	137	64	58	134	55	144	49	146	159	155	42	38	1379
	138	68	131	65	130	59	50	145	56	143	37	45	152	160	1379
	57	129	66	132	67	140	148	51	142	53	163	150	47	34	1379
	63	135	60	133	139	61	141	54	147	52	33	168	158	35	1379
	13	20	17	187	181	183	179	12	11	182	7	192	1	194	1379
	188	171	28	25	175	21	170	24	174	9	2	193	8	191	1379
	178	26	169	172	22	176	27	173	23	19	196	3	190	5	1379
	15	177	180	10	16	14	18	185	186	184	189	6	195	4	1379
	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379	1379

There are total 45 examples. These can be downloaded as **pdf file** from author's site [3] or at the link given above

6 Magic Squares of Order 16

Below are few examples of magic square of order 16 formed by cornered magic squares of order 6

1	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	2056											
8	2	254	256	243	13	245	7	40	34	222	224	211	45	213	39	2056
5	20	238	236	242	17	18	252	43	49	50	210	204	52	206	214	2056
6	19	237	21	15	240	239	251	38	208	207	47	53	51	205	219	2056
11	23	234	31	228	25	230	246	221	63	196	57	198	55	202	36	2056
253	241	16	26	229	32	227	4	37	58	197	64	195	201	56	220	2056
248	233	24	232	27	226	29	9	216	200	59	194	61	209	48	41	2056
247	235	22	225	30	231	28	10	215	193	62	199	60	203	54	42	2056
250	255	3	1	14	244	12	249	218	223	35	33	46	212	44	217	2056
104	98	158	160	147	109	149	103	72	66	190	192	179	77	181	71	2056
101	139	118	127	132	121	134	156	69	95	164	89	166	171	86	188	2056
102	145	112	122	133	128	131	155	70	90	165	96	163	169	88	187	2056
107	137	120	136	123	130	125	150	75	168	91	162	93	177	80	182	2056
157	119	138	129	126	135	124	100	189	161	94	167	92	87	170	68	2056
152	116	142	140	146	114	113	105	184	82	81	178	172	84	174	73	2056
151	115	141	117	111	143	144	106	183	175	176	79	85	83	173	74	2056
154	159	99	97	110	148	108	153	186	191	67	65	78	180	76	185	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

2	Inder J. Taneja		https://numbers-magic.com/		https://inderjtaneja.com/		@IJTANEJA	2056								
8	2	254	256	243	13	245	7	40	34	222	224	211	45	213	39	2056
5	31	228	25	230	235	22	252	43	203	54	63	196	57	198	214	2056
6	26	229	32	227	233	24	251	38	209	48	58	197	64	195	219	2056
11	232	27	226	29	241	16	246	221	201	56	200	59	194	61	36	2056
253	225	30	231	28	23	234	4	37	55	202	193	62	199	60	220	2056
248	18	17	242	236	20	238	9	216	52	206	204	210	50	49	41	2056
247	239	240	15	21	19	237	10	215	51	205	53	47	207	208	42	2056
250	255	3	1	14	244	12	249	218	223	35	33	46	212	44	217	2056
104	98	158	160	147	109	149	103	72	66	190	192	179	77	181	71	2056
101	113	114	146	140	116	142	156	69	84	174	172	178	81	82	188	2056
102	144	143	111	117	115	141	155	70	83	173	85	79	176	175	187	2056
107	127	132	121	134	119	138	150	75	87	170	95	164	89	166	182	2056
157	122	133	128	131	137	120	100	189	177	80	90	165	96	163	68	2056
152	136	123	130	125	145	112	105	184	169	88	168	91	162	93	73	2056
151	129	126	135	124	139	118	106	183	171	86	161	94	167	92	74	2056
154	159	99	97	110	148	108	153	186	191	67	65	78	180	76	185	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

4	Inder J. Taneja		https://numbers-magic.com/		https://inderjtaneja.com/		@IJTANEJA	2056								
80	177	17	242	11	244	249	8	101	155	154	104	150	151	108	105	2056
178	79	12	243	18	241	247	10	156	102	103	153	107	106	149	152	2056
77	180	246	13	240	15	255	2	109	148	231	26	35	224	29	226	2056
179	78	239	16	245	14	9	248	147	110	237	20	30	225	36	223	2056
183	74	4	250	256	3	6	252	146	111	229	28	228	31	222	33	2056
76	181	253	7	1	254	5	251	112	145	27	230	221	34	227	32	2056
182	75	89	167	166	92	85	172	144	113	24	234	232	238	22	21	2056
73	184	168	90	91	165	171	86	115	142	23	233	25	19	235	236	2056
57	58	202	196	60	198	88	169	141	116	93	162	163	96	125	132	2056
200	199	55	61	59	197	170	87	114	143	164	95	94	161	131	126	2056
71	188	65	190	63	194	121	136	42	216	214	220	39	40	130	127	2056
66	189	72	187	193	64	135	122	41	215	43	37	218	217	128	129	2056
192	67	186	69	201	56	134	123	45	212	53	206	47	208	81	176	2056
185	70	191	68	195	62	124	133	219	38	48	207	54	205	175	82	2056
117	139	138	120	97	159	158	100	211	46	210	49	204	51	84	173	2056
140	118	119	137	160	98	99	157	213	44	203	52	209	50	174	83	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

8	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	2056											
6	252	250	256	3	4	75	78	183	178	21	22	238	232	24	234	2056
5	251	7	1	254	253	184	83	174	73	236	235	19	25	23	233	2056
9	248	17	242	11	244	76	173	84	181	35	224	29	226	27	230	2056
255	2	12	243	18	241	177	176	81	80	30	225	36	223	229	28	2056
247	10	246	13	240	15	180	82	175	77	228	31	222	33	237	20	2056
249	8	239	16	245	14	79	179	74	182	221	34	227	32	231	26	2056
111	148	112	141	144	115	127	132	121	134	87	172	88	165	168	91	2056
114	119	137	140	118	143	122	133	128	131	90	95	161	164	94	167	2056
147	138	120	117	139	110	136	123	130	125	171	162	96	93	163	86	2056
142	109	145	116	113	146	129	126	135	124	166	85	169	92	89	170	2056
195	62	71	188	65	190	99	102	159	154	53	206	47	208	213	44	2056
201	56	66	189	72	187	160	107	150	97	48	207	54	205	211	46	2056
193	64	192	67	186	69	100	149	108	157	210	49	204	51	219	38	2056
63	194	185	70	191	68	153	152	105	104	203	52	209	50	45	212	2056
60	198	196	202	58	57	156	106	151	101	40	39	220	214	42	216	2056
59	197	61	55	199	200	103	155	98	158	217	218	37	43	41	215	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

27	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	2056											
8	2	254	256	243	13	245	7	40	34	222	224	211	45	213	39	2056
5	20	238	236	242	17	18	252	43	49	50	210	204	52	206	214	2056
6	19	237	21	15	240	239	251	38	208	207	47	53	51	205	219	2056
11	23	234	31	228	25	230	246	221	63	196	57	198	55	202	36	2056
253	241	16	26	229	32	227	4	37	58	197	64	195	201	56	220	2056
248	233	24	232	27	226	29	9	216	200	59	194	61	209	48	41	2056
247	235	22	225	30	231	28	10	215	193	62	199	60	203	54	42	2056
250	255	3	1	14	244	12	249	218	223	35	33	46	212	44	217	2056
92	170	89	166	85	169	71	188	65	190	116	146	109	142	113	145	2056
173	160	162	93	99	84	66	189	72	187	149	134	119	140	121	108	2056
81	98	104	153	159	176	192	67	186	69	143	122	129	128	135	114	2056
171	161	101	156	96	86	185	70	191	68	147	118	127	130	139	110	2056
167	100	155	102	157	90	79	180	73	182	105	124	126	131	133	152	2056
174	94	154	103	163	83	74	181	80	179	150	137	132	125	120	107	2056
82	158	95	164	97	175	184	75	178	77	106	136	138	117	123	151	2056
88	87	168	91	172	165	177	78	183	76	112	111	148	115	144	141	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

42	Inder J. Taneja	https://numbers-magic.com/	https://inderjtaneja.com/	@IJTANEJA	2056											
81	79	177	175	174	84	172	86	87	170	198	199	60	62	56	196	2056
176	178	80	82	83	173	85	171	89	168	200	66	192	63	193	57	2056
103	154	127	132	121	134	139	118	94	163	55	191	65	194	64	202	2056
153	104	122	133	128	131	137	120	167	90	61	58	197	195	201	59	2056
105	152	136	123	130	125	145	112	166	91	238	21	22	232	24	234	2056
151	106	129	126	135	124	119	138	92	165	19	236	235	25	23	233	2056
150	107	114	113	146	140	116	142	169	88	35	224	29	226	27	230	2056
148	109	143	144	111	117	115	141	164	93	30	225	36	223	229	28	2056
110	147	102	161	97	159	95	100	156	158	228	31	222	33	237	20	2056
108	149	155	96	160	98	162	157	101	99	221	34	227	32	231	26	2056
184	69	190	71	211	46	53	206	47	208	17	242	11	244	249	8	2056
74	75	182	183	45	212	48	207	54	205	12	243	18	241	247	10	2056
68	78	179	189	219	38	210	49	204	51	246	13	240	15	255	2	2056
72	181	76	185	213	44	203	52	209	50	239	16	245	14	9	248	2056
187	180	77	70	42	216	214	220	40	39	4	3	256	250	6	252	2056
186	188	67	73	41	215	43	37	217	218	253	254	1	7	5	251	2056
2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056	2056

There are total 118 examples. These can be downloaded as **pdf file** from author's site [3] or at the link given above. Study on magic squares of orders 18, 20, etc. with cornered magic squares of order 6 shall be given elsewhere.

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